

Economic Benefits of Energy Storage and Price-aware Demand Response for Future Smart Cities

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Abstract—As new goals were set in terms of reliability and sustainability in urban power grids, demand response (DR) programs have gained remarkable attention for their benefits offered to both grid and customers. The scope of this work is to analyze the impact of different types of demand side management (DSM) programs in Smart City context, considering the presence of local renewable energy sources (RESs) and storage devices. In this paper, a scheduling optimization scheme for an urban distribution network is presented, aiming to reduce the total operation cost. In this regard, a dual-objective model has been developed, that influences the balance between the global operational cost and the total load curtailment provided by the DR programs, while satisfying the technological constraints of the system.

Index Terms— Demand Response, energy storage system, dual-objective optimization, renewable energy sources, Smart City.

I. INTRODUCTION

Hosting more than 50% of the global population, urban areas are currently responsible for 75% of the world energy consumption [1]. Under these circumstances, cities require new and intelligent infrastructures capable of meeting the needs of their citizens and the business environment. Modern monitoring, optimization and control technologies come as effective solutions to the new requirements and challenges of urban communities, enabling the development of Smart City concept. Smart cities represent urban areas aiming to improve the quality of life by using different types of sensors and information and communication technologies (ICT) to collect data for an efficient management of local assets and resources [2].

A fundamental component underlying the urban evolution is the energy infrastructure, which is currently undergoing a radical transformation. Composed mainly of distribution networks, the urban power grids are motivated by the increased demand and the new environmental regulations to transit from the traditional centralized control, based on bulk generation units, to smart decentralized operation, including small-scaled,

distributed generation and energy storage systems (ESS) [3]. In the scenario of an expected increase of 40% in energy demand for the next decade, and the potential of clean renewable energy to meet a great quantity of this demand, energy management programs represent an essential solution to urban power grid development and sustainability, while ensuring accessible energy prices for the customers. Assisted by the advanced metering infrastructure (AMI), that allows a bi-directional information flow between electricity utilities and end-users [4], DR programs can encourage new consumption patterns, for both short-term and long-term perspectives. The smart meters' capability to record the energy consumption on several time-of-use periods of a day allows the utility to offer different customized tariffs to the end users [5].

Due to their functional and economic benefits, the DR programs have attracted many researchers' attention in the past few years, in order to solve the day-ahead scheduling problem for smart distribution networks (SDNs). The authors of [6] propose an energy and reserve scheduling approach to manage generation and consumption in microgrids, based on DR programs, as development basis for future smart distribution systems. In [7], the optimal power dispatch in a smart distribution network is studied, considering demand response and wind generation, while in [8] a price-aware residential DR model, which incorporates renewable sources and the electric vehicle, is presented. The optimal allocation of renewable sources, energy storage and demand response is also analyzed in [9], aiming to reduce via information gap decision theory the unintended costs due to the uncertainties of RESs.

Our contribution consists in developing an efficient management framework in order to achieve an urban distribution network with minimal operation cost. In this regard, a bi-objective non-linear model is proposed, aiming to obtain the optimal scheduling of DR, RESs and ESS in distribution systems, considering industrial and residential customers participation. In order to analyze the impact of DSM strategies, several price-aware DR programs are

assessed. To solve the scheduling problem, is important to identify the balance between the global operational cost and the total load shifting provided by the DR programs, thus the ϵ -constraint method is applied to determine the optimal solution.

II. DEMAND RESPONSE PROGRAMS

Demand side management (DSM) refers to any incentive service given by energy suppliers to influence the customers' consumption. There are various forms of DMS programs deployed, depending on the sector and user's type, the required degree of reliability and many other factors.

1) Incentive-based Programs of Demand Response

Incentive-based DR programs consist of predefined incentives and penalties aiming to encourage users into participating in electricity markets in order to respond to power system operational needs [10].

Direct Load Control Management (DLC) programs refer to services in which the system operators adopt incentives for users so they can remotely interrupt customer's appliances on short notice during peak or critical periods. There are limited frequency and duration of interruptions in this program.

Interruptible Demand (I/C) is based on the assumption that customers will reduce their consumption in critical times announced by system operators (for 30 to 60 minutes), otherwise they are penalized. Users who can participate in such programs have a consumption of 200kW - 3MW. However, critical loads, such as hospitals, schools, or institutions that carry out 24/7 continuous activities, cannot be included in this program.

Emergency Demand Response Programs (EDRP) is implemented by customers willing to receive incentives from the system operator to contribute in critical conditions when the reliability of the system is threatened, but unlike the previous programs, customers are not penalized if they choose not to participate.

Load Reduction Acting as Capacity (CAP) is offered by an independent system operator (ISO) or the regional transmission organization (RTO). The customers are payed an incentive for curtailing their load during critical conditions, but they are not penalized for refusing to interrupt their demand. Similar to an insurance, this program requires a fee, even if crucial events do not occur.

Demand Bidding/Buyback Program (DB) is a demand nodding/buyback programs that encourages large customers (industrial and commercial loads) to offer their prices at which they are willing to reduce the consumption or their curtailed load amounts based on predefined price by ISO.

Ancillary Services (AS) programs are also an incentive-based DR program that allows customers to offer prices for load reduction in critical situations, when the system reliability is at risk. In these circumstances, users should

implement load reduction within minutes to ensure the system stability.

2) Price-based programs

Price-based programs of DR refer to time-varying electricity tariffs for different times, when customers can react based on these fluctuating costs [11].

Time of Use (TOU) defines three levels of electricity prices: peak, off peak, and average. This type of DR is common and suitable especially for residential customers. The price values at each level may be different, depending on the seasons or day on the week, but the main tariff scheme including the three level steps will remain constant.

Critical Peak Price (CPP) program consists of two levels of electricity price. One level is characterized by high rates of prices (during peak hours), and the other is for off-peak hours, these prices setting taking place on certain days of the year.

Real Time Price (RTP), unlike TOU and CPP that imply pre-defined tariffs, is related to the volatility of hourly electricity prices within 24 hours. Prices are continuously variable throughout the day, following electricity price fluctuations in the wholesale market.

III. PROBLEM FORMULATION

The following optimal scheduling model will be applied for the network operation management, in order to reduce the total operation costs in a urban distribution system, while satisfying all its technical constraints, including bus voltage and line currents limits.

A. Objective functions

Two objective functions are considered in this study. The first objective function, defining the total operational costs to be minimized in a day-ahead market, is formulated in (1). The first term of the equation represents the cost of real power purchased from the main grid, P_E^S , while the second and third term is associated to the costs of the solar panel generation (c_{PV}) and storage unit operation (c_{ESS}). The incentives paid to the customers for their participation in DR programs by reducing their active power consumption (c_{DR}) are also introduced in this equation, by the fourth term.

$$\begin{aligned} \min OF_1 = & \sum_{t \in T} c_S \cdot P_t^S + \sum_{j \in RES} \sum_{t \in T} c_{PV} \cdot P_{j,t}^{PV} \\ & + \sum_{j \in ESS} \sum_{t \in T} c_{ESS} \cdot (P_{j,t}^{stg} - P_{j,t}^{inj}) - \sum_{j \in N} \sum_{t \in T} c_{DR} \cdot P_{j,t}^{DR} \end{aligned} \quad (1)$$

Additionally to the economic goal, a second objective function is introduced by (2), where the total unmet power demand is minimized. Despite the financial benefits of DR programs, the model must ensure the supply of as much demand as possible.

$$\min OF_2 = \sum_{j \in N} \sum_{t \in T} P_{j,t}^{DR} \quad (2)$$

B. Constraints

Power flow constraints:

$$P_{j,t}^{net} = U_{j,t} \sum_{k=1}^N U_{k,t} \times [G_{jk} \cos(\theta_{jk}) + B_{jk} \sin(\theta_{jk})] \quad (3)$$

$$Q_{j,t}^{net} = U_{j,t} \sum_{k=1}^N U_{k,t} \times [G_{jk} \sin(\theta_{jk}) - B_{jk} \cos(\theta_{jk})] \quad (4)$$

where:

$$P_{j,t}^{net} = P_{j,t}^L - P_{j,t}^{DR} - P_t^S - P_{j,t}^{PV} - P_{j,t}^{inj} + P_{j,t}^{stg} \quad (5)$$

$$Q_{j,t}^{net} = Q_{j,t}^L - Q_{j,t}^{DR} - Q_t^S \quad (6)$$

The sets of equations (3)-(6) define the active and reactive power balance at each bus j . $U_{j,t}$ represents the voltage magnitude at bus j in time frame t , $U_{k,t}$ is the voltage magnitude at bus k that is connected to bus j , while θ_{jk} define the voltage angle between these two buses. $P_{j,t}^L$ and $Q_{j,t}^L$ are power load at bus j in hour t , P_t^S and Q_t^S are the purchased powers from the main grid at the slack bus, while $P_{j,t}^{DR}$ and $Q_{j,t}^{DR}$ represent the shifted demand through the DR programs at bus j in time frame t .

In order to obtain a constant power factor at bus j after the load curtailment, the following restriction is applied for $Q_{j,t}^{DR}$:

$$Q_{j,t}^{DR} = P_{j,t}^{DR} \cdot (Q_{j,t}^L / P_{j,t}^L) \quad (7)$$

Constraints (8) and (9) set the bus voltage and branch flow capacity limits, while (10) establish the generation limits of the solar panels considered in the study.

$$U_j^{\min} \leq U_{j,t} \leq U_j^{\max} \quad (8)$$

$$-S_{jk}^{\max} \leq S_{j,k,t} \leq S_{jk}^{\max} \quad (9)$$

$$P_{g,j}^{\min} \leq P_{j,t}^{PV} \leq P_{g,j}^{\max} \quad (10)$$

An energy storage unit based on lead-acid batteries is also considered in the analyzed system. The storage unit is set to provide a unitary power factor, thus the reactive power injection is neglected, and the storage unit is modelled only by the injected and stored active power, $P_{j,t}^{inj}$ and $P_{j,t}^{stg}$. The scope of the energy storage device is to provide power to the system during high energy prices periods, while charging during low prices periods. Coordinated with the local PV generation units, the energy storage system participates in the load peak reduction and the renewable energy sources integration, based on its ability to shift load and generation in other day time periods.

Constraints (11)-(14) model the optimal operation of the storage unit. In order to avoid the battery's overcharging and over-discharging, (11) and (12) ensure the injected and stored power limits between the minimum and maximum capacity. The operating mode of the battery (charging/discharging) is determined by the binary variable, λ_t^{ESS} . In this manner, the state of charging is defined by the value $\lambda_t^{ESS} = 0$, resulting in no injection at time t according to (11), while the value $\lambda_t^{ESS} = 1$ denote the discharging state of the battery, corresponding to no charging according to (12).

In this model, a self-discharging rate β^{ESS} is considered, depending on the reduction or increasing of charge. In (13), the state of charge of the battery (SOC) is determined based on the remaining available capacity from the previous period $t-1$, while taking into account also the charging and discharging efficiencies, $\eta_{j,t}^{stg}$ and $\eta_{j,t}^{inj}$.

$$P_{j,\min}^{inj} \cdot \lambda_{j,t}^{ESS} \leq P_{j,t}^{inj} \leq P_{j,\max}^{inj} \cdot \lambda_{j,t}^{ESS} \quad (11)$$

$$P_{j,\min}^{stg} \cdot (1 - \lambda_{j,t}^{ESS}) \leq P_{j,t}^{stg} \leq P_{j,\max}^{stg} \cdot (1 - \lambda_{j,t}^{ESS}) \quad (12)$$

$$SOC_{j,t} = (1 - \beta_j^{ESS}) SOC_{j,t-1} + \left[\eta_{j,t}^{stg} \cdot P_{j,t}^{stg} - \frac{P_{j,t}^{inj}}{\eta_{j,t}^{inj}} \right] \quad (13)$$

$$\sum_t \lambda_{j,t}^{ESS} \leq h \quad (14)$$

In order to prolong the ESS lifetime, a number of autonomy hours is imposed in (14) for the system charging/discharging scheduling.

In this research, the effectiveness of price-based demand response programs is analyzed. The users involved in price-based programs contribute to the network operation enhancement by reducing their electrical energy consumption, receiving incentives in return from the DSO. The following constraints define the load curtailment preferences. In (15), the maximum accumulated unmet demand for each DR provider j is limited throughout the time horizon (24 hours) to a predefined acceptable quantity DR_j , while (16) enforce the maximum acceptable unmet load for each time frame.

$$\sum_{t \in T} P_{j,t}^{DR} \leq DR_j \quad (15)$$

$$P_{j,t}^{DR} \leq P_j^{DR,\max} \quad (16)$$

C. The ϵ -constraint method

Multi-objective programming problems imply the simultaneous optimization of two or more conflicting objectives subject to certain constraints. The method approached in this study to solve the bi-objective DR problem is the ϵ -constraint strategy. Since the method cannot identify a unique solution for both objectives, the most acceptable solution is searched among Pareto optimal solutions.

The ϵ -constraint method is applied for optimizing the first objective function, while the second objective function is used as constraint.

$$\min OF_1(x)$$

subject to:

$$OF_2(x) \leq E$$

$$E_i = \max(OF_2) - \left(\frac{\max(OF_2) - \min(OF_2)}{n} \right) \times i,$$

where $i = 0, 1, \dots, n$, and \max and \min represent the maximum and minimum values of the second objective function, respectively.

IV. CASE STUDY

In order to perform an analysis of the optimization algorithm for the DR scheduling problem, a case study was defined on the modified IEEE 33-bus system. The scheduling optimization problem will be analyzed with a fixed number of PV generation units, along with DR participants in the network. 6 users are considered to participate in the DR program (based on the largest capacity), more specific the loads connected in bus 7, 14, 21, 25, 26, and 32, respectively.

Figure 1. The modified IEEE 33-bus test system

Three PV units are deployed in the test network at bus 12, 24 and 30, characterized by the forecasted generation illustrated in Fig. 2.

Figure 2. Generation forecast for the PV units

In order to overcome the stochastic nature of the RESs to be integrated in the grid, a battery energy storage system is also considered in the network, at bus 19, presenting a capacity of 1 MW.

Load forecast error and power generation errors of PV units are assumed to be of 5-10%.

Both residential and industrial users are considered to participate in the DR strategy, to contribute to the demand curve flattening and to increase the cost savings of the network. The residential users are equipped with different base load appliance and shiftable appliances. The corresponding consumption curves of the two typical loads are presented in Fig. 3.

Figure 3. Load profiles

Three pricing policies are considered in this research, including time of use, critical peak pricing and real-time pricing offered by the utility company.

Figure 4. Price-based DR programs under study

During the peak demand hours, the distribution system operator will have a provision to decrease up to 10% of DR participating load, as it will pay incentives of 0.98€/kW according to [12].

V. NUMERICAL RESULTS

This paper proposes a price-aware DR strategy which assembles the optimal demand scheduling with PV and energy storage units. The study assesses the economic benefits of three DR programs based on the comparison to the base case (without DR), in order to emphasize the DR impact on distribution networks operation.

The Fig. 5. shows the optimal operation scheduling for the energy storage unit. As can be seen, the power injection by the storage system is scheduled wisely during the peak demand or high grid price hours, to meet the demand requirements. The charging of the battery takes place during the off-peak/low grid price hours, or during the PV high generation period (12 pm to 16 pm).

Figure 5. The hourly operation of the ESS

Fig. 6-7 illustrate the DR participation in the optimal day-ahead scheduling of the two types of users considered in the study. Must be observed that the analyzed DSM strategies allow the users to reduce their power consumption during the peak demand hours (8 am to 10 pm), in order to reduce the operational cost of the network.

Figure 6. Demand side participation for industrial users

Figure 7. Demand side participation for residential users

The impact of the price-aware operation scheduling can be observed in Fig. 8, where the resulted consumption profiles corresponding to the applied DR tariffs are illustrated.

The system load in Fig. 8 shows that the peak hours are present between 9 am to 12 pm, and 5 pm to 10 pm, respectively. The curve of the power imported from the substation changes, as result of DR programs implementation, leading to the load shifting to lower energy prices periods (1 am to 7 am).

Figure 8. Power purchased from the substation

Based on the obtained load curves, several operational parameters have been compared in Table I, including the peak load, peak reduction with respect to the base case (without DR), the valley load, the peak to average ratio and the total cost. Peak reduction can be observed for all three DR policies, while a lower cost is ensured by reducing the consumption during high price periods (8 am to 10 pm).

TABLE I. SIMULATION RESULTS

	Base case	TOU	CPP	RTP
Peak [kW]	1767.667	1682.342	1612.237	1677.27
Peak reduction [%]	-	4.827	8.793	5.114
Valley [kW]	859.967	902.725	906.391	898.626
Peak to average	1.369	1.338	1.278	1.334
Total cost [€]	342.143	256.405	238.261	278.14

Based on these values, it can be seen that the CPP program provides the best results, including the highest peak load reduction and also the total cost of operating the network, while ensuring a lower peak to average ratio than the base case and the other two DR programs.

VI. CONCLUSIONS

In urban distribution networks, where the generation capacity is limited or insufficient, the flexible load programs can prove themselves efficient mechanisms in power grid regulation.

The motivation of undergoing this study is the promising benefits of DR policies based on a price-aware scheme in enhancing the total operation cost, while maintaining the functional parameters of the grid in optimal ranges. In this regard, a bi-objective optimization model was presented in this paper, which aims to solve the optimal scheduling problem of RES, ESS and DR operation in distribution systems.

The results show a significant reduction in the total cost associated with the consumption of electric power due to DR programs deployment. Three price-aware programs have been

considered in this study: TOU, CPP and RTP. The simulations report around 26.52% cost savings for the TOU policy, 30.36% for CPP, and 18.71% for the RTP, respectively.

Additional to the economic benefits, the variation of the total demand is mitigated compared to the original demand scheduling, resulting in the flattening of the load curve. In this manner, the investment deferral in upgrading the existent energy infrastructures is obtained, by the efficient management of local resources, including flexible loads, small-scale renewable energy sources and storage systems.

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